

DESIGN OF ANTENNA-EMBEDDED COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURE USING OPEN CONDITION FOR WIDE BANDWIDTH AND HIGH GAIN

Chi Sang You¹, Dong Seob Kim¹, and Woonbong Hwang¹

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology
San 31, Pohang, Kyungbuk, 790-784, Rep. of Korea*

SUMMARY: The present study aims to design electrically and structurally effective antenna structures. The basic design concept is a composite sandwich structure in which microstrip antenna is embedded and this is termed *composite smart structure* (CSS). The most important outstanding problem is that composite materials of structural function cannot be used without reducing antenna efficiency. This is a significant design problem that needs to be solved in practical applications. Therefore, the effect of facesheet on antenna performances is studied in the first stage. Changes in the gain of microstrip antenna due to facesheet have been determined. ‘*Open condition*’ is defined when gain is maximized. The open condition can be made with the thickness of outer facesheet by controlling its position. In the design of CSS, glass/epoxy composites and Nomex honeycomb are used with exploiting open condition. Experiments, confirm that the gain is improved and the bandwidth is also as wide as specified in our requirements.

KEYWORDS: Antenna, Honeycomb, Sandwich Structure, Smart Structure, Communication

INTRODUCTION

In the past ten years, researches have been performed on the embedding of antennas in load-bearing structural surfaces of aircraft in order to improve both structural efficiency and antenna performances [1-3]. The research program in [1] successfully designed, fabricated, and confirmed the structural integrity of a multifunction antenna component panel subjected to realistic aircraft flight load conditions. Use of a composite roof structure in a military truck with multiple antenna reception allows the latest in communication and entertainment reception needs within a light-weight and durable self-contained structure [4]. Through the innovative integration of antenna elements, amplifiers and ground plane, the reception quality and manufacturability of vehicles are expected to be significantly improved. The articles published to date indicate that the technology has had some spectacular success in its initial stages, but little has been published about the problems that remain to be overcome for use in an operational vehicle. The most important outstanding problem is that structurally effective materials cannot be used without reducing antenna efficiency. Load-bearing antenna structures, designed through compromise between electrical and mechanical performances [5-7] have few benefits, comparing with previously installed antennas.

The present study aims to design electrically and structurally effective antenna structures. This is termed *composite smart structure* (CSS). Structurally effective materials with high electrical loss must not reduce antenna efficiency. Design is focused electrically toward high gain and wide bandwidth, and mechanically toward high strength, stiffness and environmental

tolerance. *An open condition* [8] is used in order to allow composite materials without loss of antenna efficiency and give good gain and bandwidth. Stacked-patch microstrip antenna is used for wideband performance. A sandwich structure composed of GFRP and Nomex honeycomb is used to give good mechanical performances. After fabrication of the designed structure, its electrical performances are measured.

BASIC CONCEPT OF CSS

The fundamental design concept of the CSS panel is an organic composite sandwich panel in which microstrip antenna layer is inserted, as shown in Fig. 1.

Microstrip antennas can be used in high-performance aircraft, spacecraft, and satellite and missile applications, where constraints include size, weight, cost, performance, ease of installation, and aerodynamic profile. This antenna is low-profile, conformable to planar and nonplanar surfaces and simple and inexpensive to manufacture using modern printed-circuit technology.

The conventional sandwich construction consists of two relatively dense and stiff facesheets that are bonded to either side of a low-density core. The facesheets carry bending-induced axial loads, and the core sustains shear stresses as well as compressive stresses normal to the plate. It also helps to resist buckling of the facesheets under axial compressive loading. The core usually has low in-plane and flexural stiffness compared to the facesheets, but it can have significant transverse stiffness and shear stiffness. The presence of the core moves the facesheets away from the neutral axis, enhancing the bending resistance provided by the facesheets.

Fig. 1: Basic concept

DESIGN PROCEDURES

Antenna performances are sought in the frequency range 11.7 to 12.75 GHz and the antenna layer is designed for a central frequency of 12.2 GHz. Stacked-patch microstrip antenna is preferred, in which stacked radiating patches give wide bandwidth, via the coupling of the dual resonance system as shown in Fig. 2.

After the antenna layer, outer facesheet is next designed. Glass/Epoxy composite is used as the facesheet material. However, the outstanding problem is that composite materials of structural function cannot be used without reducing antenna efficiency. This is a significant design problem that needs to be solved in practical applications. Therefore, the effect of facesheet on antenna performances is studied by transmission/reflection methods.

A schematic diagram of the antenna covered by the facesheet is shown in Fig. 3(a). The maximum gain condition by the facesheet. is satisfied when the reflection coefficient Γ_t is equal to one and it depends on the thickness, position, and properties of the facesheet. This maximum gain condition by facesheet is named *open condition* after open-circuited line. The reflection coefficient, Γ_t , is expressed as follows:

$$\Gamma_t = \frac{\Gamma_{01} - \Gamma_{01} e^{-2jk_1 d} + \Gamma_{01}^2 e^{-2jk_0 l} - e^{-2j(k_1 d - k_0 l)}}{1 - \Gamma_{01}^2 e^{-2jk_1 d} + \Gamma_{01} e^{-2jk_0 l} - \Gamma_{01} e^{-2j(k_1 d - k_0 l)}} \quad (1)$$

$$\Gamma_{01} = \frac{\sqrt{\mu_r} - \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}{\sqrt{\mu_r} + \sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (2)$$

where,

- Γ_t : total reflection coefficient on facesheet
- Γ_{01} : partial reflection coefficient from free space to facesheet
- k_1 : wave number in facesheet
- k_0 : wave number in free space
- d : thickness of facesheet
- l : position of facesheet from ground plane
- ϵ_r : relative permittivity of facesheet
- μ_r : relative permeability of facesheet

The relation between the thickness and position of the facesheet in the open condition is shown in Fig. 3(b). For this curve, a facesheet of $0.08 \lambda_g$ -thickness (1 mm) is selected, then the distance from the ground plane is $0.62 \lambda_0$ in the open condition. Theoretical result shows the reflection coefficient Γ_t varies by not more than 10 % over about 1 GHz-bandwidth with the facesheet of $0.08 \lambda_g$ -thickness, therefore it gives a bandwidth exceeding 1 GHz as well as a gain increase.

Fig. 2: Antenna layer

(a) Antenna covered by facesheet

(b) Facesheet position in open condition

Fig. 3: Facesheet effect on antenna

The actual position of the facesheet is always beneath that predicted by theory, so it is best found by slowly lowering the facesheet from the position predicted by theory. Fig. 4 shows the full structure of CSS before and after assembly, in which the position of the outer facesheet depends on the honeycomb thickness and is determined by experimental tuning. Based on the results, honeycomb of 10 mm-thickness is selected.

EXPERIMENTS

Manufacture of the CSS is a sequential process. First, antenna layer is fabricated and then designed facesheets and honeycomb are prepared. For the facesheet of 1 mm-thickness, Glass/Epoxy prepregs of 8 plies is symmetrically laid up with cross-ply and then cured in hot press (125 °C for 90 minutes under force of 5 kgf/cm²). Each layer is bonded on the top or bottom of another one in designed sequence by epoxy film adhesive. The assembly, covered by the vacuum bag, is then cured in an autoclave according to the recommended curing cycle for this adhesive (125 °C for 90 minutes under pressure of 3 kgf/cm²).

After fabrication, the antenna performances are measured and compared with those of the antenna determined before insertion. The reflection coefficient is measured with a Network Analyzer 8510 under laboratory conditions and radiation patterns are obtained at compact range in Postech. Radiation patterns are measured at three frequencies, 11.7, 12.2, and 12.75 GHz, to reveal patterns in bandwidth. Gains are then calculated by comparing amplitudes of

the electric field with that of a standard gain horn antenna (SAS-585, SAS-586, A.H. Systems inc.).

Fig. 5 shows the reflection coefficient of CSS. The reflection coefficient becomes a little higher in CSS than in the antenna, but the bandwidth is still as required in our frequency range of 11.7 to 12.75 GHz. Fig. 6 shows radiation patterns with gain. The gain increased from 8.2 to 11.2 dBi in CSS, which gives rise to the open condition. Radiation patterns in the relevant frequency range are shown in Fig. 7. The gain at 11.7 and 12.75 GHz is respectively 11.91 and 12.25 dBi, and the radiation patterns are almost same over the bandwidth. This is a consequence of the chosen design.

CONCLUSIONS

CSS is a composite sandwich structure with which a microstrip antenna is integrated. Glass/Epoxy of structural function can be used as a facesheet material without reducing the antenna efficiency, by exploiting open condition that involves both the thickness and position of the top facesheet. Experiments, confirm that the gain is improved and the bandwidth is also as wide as specified in our requirements.

The CSS concept makes it possible to design antenna structures with structurally effective materials. The concept can be extended to provide a useful guide for manufacturers of structural body panels as well as antenna designers.

Fig. 4: Assembly procedure of CSS

Fig. 5: Reflection coefficient

Fig. 6: Radiation pattern (12.2 GHz)

Fig. 7: Radiation patterns in Bandwidth

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the Center for Intelligent Surgery System (CISS- 02-PJ3-PG6-EV04-0003) and Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Energy (industry-education cooperation projects), for which authors are grateful.

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